

Construction of Numerical PVT-Models for the Bulla-Daniz Gas-Condensate Field Based on Laboratory Experiments on Reservoir Fluid Samples

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ABSTRACT:

PVT analysis is important for field-wide optimization and development. This is because we must understand the fluid's overall behavior from the reservoir to the production and processing facilities, and ultimately to the refinery. Modern computer software that uses equation of state (EOS) models to simulate experiments and illustrate fluid phase characteristics has contributed to its growth as a distinct field of study. To find the operating parameters that will maximize the surface liquid content and prolong the production plateau duration at the lowest feasible cost, PVT simulations are run. These simulations employ laboratory-derived data to fine-tune the EOS models, with the outcomes being integrated into reservoir simulation and research. The quality of the data is crucial to getting a good match between EOS and laboratory data, and for retrograde gas condensates, this can be particularly difficult because of their complex phase behavior. When utilized in reservoir simulations, an inadequate match leads to computational mistakes and unrepresentative findings, endangering the reservoir management decisions that depend on it.

Keywords: gas-condensate field, simulation model, PVT model, equation of state, adaptation process, heavy component.

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INTRODUCTION

The oil and gas industry are capital-intensive, risky, and reliant on technology. Thus, the secret to remaining in business is to minimize ambiguity. Many tests are typically performed to assess a specific parameter. For example, well testing and coring, despite their high cost, are typically used just to measure and verify the quality of permeability [1].

Until a thorough PVT analysis has been completed, no operator would assert to have known his fluid. Even in cases when basic PVT parameters on the well site are assessed using correlations, judgments made based on these assessments are typically small and have a short lifespan [10].

The Constant Composition Expansion (CCE) and Constant Volume Depletion (CVD) are the PVT tests that are most frequently advised for retrograde gas condensates. CCE simulates fluid behaviors under separator circumstances, whereas CVD duplicates events at reservoir conditions [4].

The critical temperature and the cricondentherm are the two temperatures found in retrograde gas condensate reservoirs. They can be classified as under-saturated/lean or saturated/rich depending on how close they are to the dew point curve. The reservoir fluid content and production are single phase gas at pressures higher than the dew point. Pressure drops below the dew point during depletion at constant temperature, causing liquids and condensates that were in equilibrium with the gas phase to condense. As these liquids fall out of the reservoir, capillary-induced forces trap them while they are in the wetting phase. For operators, the immobility of the stranded condensates poses a productivity challenge. The liquid droppings re-vaporize into the gaseous phase when production pressure decreases. However, the pressure at which this happens is much lower than the abandonment pressure and is therefore unachievable because it is typically limited by economics [6].

Because of the strong compositional influence linked to the formation of retrograde events, PVT measurement and analysis are essential to comprehending them. Data from the laboratory must be compared to an EOS model to account for or adjust for unmeasured features [6]. A significant obstacle to EOS tuning/matching and accurate fluid description is the gathering of non-representative fluid samples and uncertainty in lab measurements. This research used the Tempest PVTx simulator to provide techniques for validating PVT/CVD data and to address issues with unrepresentative data [3].

For this, PVT-models based on equations of state of the Van der Waals type are typically employed. The most widely utilized three-parameter Peng-Robinson equation of state in engineering practice is the well-established one [7].

The equilibrium compositions of vapor and liquid can be calculated using the equation of state, given the thermobaric circumstances and the mixture's component composition.

This makes it possible for the hydrodynamic simulator to mimic fluid composition changes, saturations, and property changes in a sequential manner.

The issue is that applying the EOS directly to a specific multicomponent hydrocarbon mixture can result in significant inaccuracies. The usual ranges are $\pm 10\%$ for bubble point (dew point) pressure, 5% for density, and 10% for the equilibria of composition phases [8]. These mistakes typically have the following causes:

1. Inadequate details regarding the composition and percentage.
2. The PVT model's heavy components (beginning with C7) are a combination of isomers of aromatic hydrocarbons, cycloalkanes, alkanes, and other compounds rather than a single molecule. PVT-simulators utilize the values acquired for the mixture containing a particular ratio of these compounds by default. However, this could not apply to the study sample. Pseudo-components, the elements of C7 and higher are known with some mistake in their parameters [2].
3. While the properties of a gas are quite precisely described by the modern cubic equations of state, the properties of a liquid can have a significant inaccuracy (up to 5%).
4. Inaccuracies in composition determination and/or laboratory measurement.

The consistency of the composition can be somewhat confirmed by comparing the findings of laboratory tests (e.g., by utilizing the Hoffman-Crump-Hocktot test, with Standing modification, to check the material balance of the multicomponent system, etc.) for equilibrium and monotony [8].

The parameters of the equation of state are tuned to match the actual outcomes of typical PVT experiments to increase the PVT-model's accuracy. The converse issue of fine-tuning the PVT-model to experimental data thus emerges. The goal of the article under presentation is to create useful technology to address this inverse challenge. The issues of restoring reservoir composition or feed representativeness are not considered [5].

This study is based on the adaptation process of CCE, CVD test results of the well 78 in Bulla-Daniz gas-condensate field.

The Bulla-deniz field is in the northern part of the Absheron archipelago, 55 km south of the city of Baku. The depth of the sea is 18-30 m. The geological-geophysical study of Bulla-deniz field started

in 1951. Exploration work carried out in 1951-1956 helped clarify the boundaries of the fold. In 1965, structural-exploratory drilling was started here, and at the same time deep exploratory drilling works started in the Bulla-sea area. In 1973, in the northeast wing of the fold, an industrially important product, gas-condensate was obtained from horizon VII (well No. 18) and gas-condensate in 1974 from horizon V in 1974 (well No. 18). Full industrial development of the field has been carried out since 1975. According to the results of the conducted geological exploration and drilling works, it was determined that horizons V, VII, VIII have hydrocarbon accumulations. Thermodynamic and PVT studies of gas-condensate samples were conducted based on the products of the first exploration wells. It should be noted that the measured initial pressure of the V horizon was 69.0 MPa at a depth of 5350 m, 71.3 MPa at a depth of 5750 m in the VII horizon, and 80 MPa at a depth of 6000 m in the VIII horizon. Thermodynamic studies on the Bulla-sea field were conducted in wells No. 14, 20 and 22, which were put into operation in the first years of development.

In table 1 were shown, system parameters for the PVT test before adaptation process.

Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 shows different parameters versus pressure change.

Table 1. System Properties Before Adaptation Process

	Component Properties				
	Mw	Tc (F)	Pc (bar)	Acf	Zc
N2	28.013	-232.4	33.9912	0.045	0.29162
CO2	44.01	87.9	73.8153	0.231	0.27421
C1	16	-116.67	46.0432	0.012	0.29473
C2	30.1	90.13	48.8011	0.091	0.29233
C3	44.1	206.03	42.4924	0.145	0.28906
IC4	58.1	275.03	36.4802	0.176	0.28617
C4	58.1	305.63	37.9694	0.193	0.27914
IC5	72.2	369.13	33.8119	0.227	0.27017
C5	72.2	385.73	33.6878	0.251	0.26389
C6	84	454.33	32.819	0.2738	0.27176
C7+(1)	115.772	617.302	28.0194	0.30871	0.2579
C7+(2)	227.691	890.6	18.8	0.58518	0.25487
C7+(3)	300	1020.56	16.5	1.0326	0.35108

Table 2. Characteristics of the System Prior to Undergoing the Adaptation Process

	Component Properties						
	Vc (ft3/lb-mole)	Sg (sg(Water=1))	Tb (F)	Ωa	Ωb	Para	Sv
N2	1.4427	0.47	-320.4	1	1	41	-0.193
CO2	1.5051	0.5072	-109.3	1	1	70	-0.082
C1	1.62457	0.33	-258.67	1	1	77	-0.36
C2	2.43685	0.45	-127.47	1	1	108	-0.113
C3	3.35067	0.508	-43.67	1	1	150.3	-0.086
IC4	4.26449	0.561	10.93	1	1	181.5	-0.084
C4	4.16295	0.584	31.13	1	1	189.9	-0.067
IC5	4.9	0.627	82.13	1	1	225	-0.061
C5	4.9	0.63	96.93	1	1	231.5	-0.039
C6	5.6	0.69	147.33	1	1	271	-0.01936
C7+(1)	7.33474	0.76983	272.67	1	1	355.855	0.05
C7+(2)	13.5447	0.84991	557.428	1	1	632.788	0.15
C7+(3)	23.3039	0.92035	892.673	1	1	1038.54	0.4

As per Yushchenko's [10] proposal, the final fraction of C₁₆₊ was divided into three pseudo components using the Whitson gamma-distribution model [8]. This resulted in a mole fraction of the final pseudo component being less than 0.1%. Next, the real data from the experiments on saturated condensate losses (CCE, CVD, Z-factor change, and Condensate to gas ratio (CGR) in the one-stage separation experiment).

Figure 1. Relative Volume vs Pressure Curve Before Adaptation Process

Figure 2. Liquid Dropout vs Pressure Curve Before Adaptation Process

Figure 3. Gas Z Factor vs Pressure Curve Before Adaptation Process

Figure 4. Gas Viscosity vs Pressure Curve Before Adaptation Process

Regression was used to adjust the pressure at the start of condensation in the first stage. Next, by adjusting the variation to the critical temperature and pressure, the binary interaction coefficients, and the shift parameter for the final three pseudo fractions, the regression was applied to the actual data adaption in the CCE, CVD, and separation test tests. Furthermore, we employed the shift parameter and binary interaction coefficients for components as modifiers due to their substantial mole fraction in the overall composition. In table 2 were shown, system parameters for the PVT test after adaptation process. Figures 5, 6, 7, and 8 display the best outcome following multiple regressions.

Table 3. System Properties After Adaptation Process

Component Properties					
	Mw	Tc (F)	Pc (psia)	Acf	Zc
N2	28.013	-232.4	493	0.045	0.29162
CO2	44.01	87.9	1070.6	0.231	0.27421
C1	16.043	-116.63	667.8	0.0115	0.28841
C2	30.07	90.09	707.8	0.0908	0.28427
C3	44.097	206.01	616.3	0.1454	0.28037
IC4	58.124	274.98	529.1	0.1756	0.28242
C4	58.124	305.65	550.7	0.1928	0.27359
IC5	72.151	369.1	490.4	0.2273	0.27013
C5	72.151	385.7	488.6	0.251	0.26229
C6	86.178	453.7	436.9	0.2957	0.26427
C7+	166.887	753.552	258.467	0.65032	0.26984

Table 4. Characteristics of the System Following the Completion of the Adaptation Process

Component Properties							
	Vc (ft ³ /lb-mole)	Sg (sg(Water=1))	Tb (F)	Ωa	Ωb	Para	Sv
N2	1.4427	0.47	-320.4	1	1	41	-0.193
CO2	1.5051	0.5072	-109.3	1	1	70	-0.082
C1	1.5899	0.33	-258.69	1	1	77	-0.159
C2	2.3695	0.45	-127.48	1	1	108	-0.113
C3	3.2499	0.5077	-43.67	1	1	150.3	-0.086
IC4	4.2082	0.5631	10.9	1	1	181.5	-0.084
C4	4.0803	0.5844	31.1	1	1	189.9	-0.067
IC5	4.8991	0.6247	82.12	1	1	225	-0.061
C5	4.8702	0.631	96.92	1	1	231.5	-0.039
C6	5.929	0.664	155.72	1	1	271	-0.008
C7+	13.5927	0.75107	462.682	0.87042	0.97313	476.296	0.14948

Figure 5. Relative Volume vs Pressure curve after adaptation process

Figure 6. Liquid dropout vs Pressure curve after adaptation process

Figure 7. Gas Z Factor vs Pressure curve after adaptation process

Figure 8. Gas Viscosity vs Pressure curve after adaptation process

CONCLUSION

The adaptation process starts with grouping of C_{7+} heavy components. In the initial case, there were heaviest components higher than C_{16+} . After grouping, we split process of heaviest components into three parts. Then started to play with component composition of $C_7(1)$, $C_7(2)$ and $C_7(3)$. Furthermore, we employed the shift parameter and binary interaction coefficients for components as modifiers due to their substantial mole fraction in the overall composition. Afterwards, adaptation was achieved for different parameters versus pressure.

ABBREVIATIONS

EOS – Equation of State
PVT – Pressure Volume Temperature
CCE – Constant Composition Expansion
CVD – Constant Volume Depletion
CGR – Condensate Gas Ratio

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